
PRIMES IN SHIFTED SUMS OF LUCAS SEQUENCES

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Abstract

For any $a_1, a_2, b \in \mathbb{Z}$, with $b \neq 0$, we define

$$\mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} := \mathcal{U}(a_1, b) + \mathcal{U}(a_2, b),$$

where $\mathcal{U}(a_i, b)$ is the Lucas sequence of the first kind defined by

$$u_0 = 0, \quad u_1 = 1, \quad \text{and} \quad u_n = a_i u_{n-1} + b u_{n-2} \quad \text{for all } n \geq 2,$$

and the n th term of \mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} is the sum of the n th terms of $\mathcal{U}(a_1, b)$ and $\mathcal{U}(a_2, b)$. In this article, we prove that there exist infinitely many integers b and $a_1, a_2 > 0$, with $b(a_1 + a_2) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, for which there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that each term of both of the shifted sequences $|\mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} \pm k|$ is composite and no single prime divides all terms of these sequences. We also show that when $b = 1$, there exist infinitely many integers $a \neq 0$ for which there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that both of the shifted sequences $\mathcal{W}_{1, a} \pm k$ also possess this primefree property.

1. Introduction

For a given sequence $\mathcal{S} = (s_n)_{n \geq 0}$, and $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, we let $\mathcal{S} + k$ denote the k -shifted sequence $(s_n + k)_{n \geq 0}$. We say that $\mathcal{S} + k$ is *primefree* if $|s_n + k|$ is not prime for all $n \geq 0$ and, to rule out trivial situations, we also require that $\mathcal{S} + k$ is not a constant sequence, and that no single prime divides all terms of $\mathcal{S} + k$. Several authors have investigated finding infinitely many values of k for various sequences \mathcal{S} such that the shifted sequences $\mathcal{S} + k$ and $\mathcal{S} - k$ are simultaneously primefree [8, 10, 7]. Such values of k are also related to a generalization of a conjecture of Polignac [2, 9]. In

this article, we investigate this primefree situation where the sequence to be shifted is actually a sum of Lucas sequences. For nonzero $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$, we let

$$\mathcal{U} := \mathcal{U}(a, b) = (u_n)_{n=0}^\infty$$

denote the Lucas sequence of the first kind defined by

$$u_0 = 0, \quad u_1 = 1, \quad \text{and} \quad u_n = au_{n-1} + bu_{n-2} \quad \text{for all } n \geq 2. \quad (1)$$

Definition 1. For a fixed nonzero integer b , and any pair (a_1, a_2) of integers, we define

$$\mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} := \mathcal{U}(a_1, b) + \mathcal{U}(a_2, b),$$

where $\mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} = (w_n)_{n=0}^\infty$, and w_n is the sum of the n th term of $\mathcal{U}(a_1, b)$ and the n th term of $\mathcal{U}(a_2, b)$.

One reason we have chosen to investigate shifted sums of these particular sequences is that the Lucas sequences have a long and rich history commencing in 1878 with the papers of Lucas [12, 13, 14]. Consequently, they are much better understood than many other sequences. For example, the terms of the Lucas sequences that possess a primitive divisor (primes that divide a term but do not divide any prior term) are completely known, thanks to the work of many mathematicians beginning with Carmichael [3] in 1913 and culminating with the deep results of Bilu, Hanrot and Voutier [1] in 2001. Another important aspect of the Lucas sequences that is particularly useful in our investigations is the concept of periodicity modulo a prime, which is explained in detail in Section 2.

Our main results are the following:

Theorem 2. *Let b be a fixed odd integer. Then there exist infinitely many pairs (a_1, a_2) of positive integers, with $a_1 + a_2$ odd, for which there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that each of the shifted sequences $\mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} \pm k$ is primefree.*

Theorem 3. *Let $b = 1$ and let $p \notin \{2, 17, 19\}$ be prime. If $a \equiv m \pmod{646p}$, where $0 \leq m \leq 646p - 1$, and m satisfies one of the 16 systems of congruences*

$$\begin{aligned} x &\equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ x &\equiv -1 \pmod{p} \\ x &\equiv r \pmod{17}, \quad \text{where } r \in \{\pm 1, \pm 4, \pm 5, \pm 6\} \\ x &\equiv \pm 4 \pmod{19}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

then there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that each of the sequences $\mathcal{W}_{1, a} \pm k$ is primefree.

In particular, if $p = 3$ in Theorem 3, then there exist infinitely many positive integers k such that each of the sequences $\mathcal{W}_{1, a} \pm k$ is primefree for every $a \equiv m$

(mod 1938), where

$$m \in \{80, 566, 650, 764, 794, 878, 992, 1106, 1220, 1364, 1478, 1592, 1706, 1790, 1820, 1934\}.$$

2. Preliminaries

We let \mathcal{U} be the Lucas sequence, as defined in (1). Although most often we write u_n for the n th term of $\mathcal{U} := \mathcal{U}(a, b)$, occasionally we write $u_n(a, b)$, or $u_n(a)$ when b is fixed, for contextual clarity. We define the *discriminant* $D(a, b)$ of $\mathcal{U}(a, b)$ as

$$D(a, b) := a^2 + 4b.$$

For a fixed b , when the context is clear, we simply write $D(a)$ instead of $D(a, b)$, as in the proof of Theorem 3.

Next, we present some basic nomenclature and facts concerning the periodicity of \mathcal{U} modulo a prime p , most of which can be found in [5]. We say that \mathcal{U} is *purely periodic* modulo p if there exists $t \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$u_{n+t} \equiv u_n \pmod{p} \tag{3}$$

for all $n \geq 0$. The minimal value of t (if it exists) such that (3) holds, is called the *least period*, or simply the *period*, of \mathcal{U} modulo p , and we denote it as $P_p := P_p(\mathcal{U}(a, b))$. It is well-known that \mathcal{U} is purely periodic modulo p if $b \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ (see, for example, [4]), and we assume throughout this article that this condition holds. The *restricted period* of \mathcal{U} modulo a prime p , which we denote $R_p := R_p(\mathcal{U}(a, b))$, is the least positive integer r such that

$$u_r \equiv 0 \pmod{p} \quad \text{and} \quad u_{n+r} \equiv M_p u_n \pmod{p}$$

for all $n \geq 0$, and some nonzero residue $M_p := M_p(\mathcal{U}(a, b))$ modulo p , called the *multiplier* of \mathcal{U} modulo p . In addition, $P_p \equiv 0 \pmod{R_p}$, and $E_p := E_p(\mathcal{U}(a, b)) = P_p/R_p$ is the order of M_p modulo p [4]. Furthermore, if $j \geq 0$ is a fixed integer, then it is easy to see that

$$u_{n+jR_p} \equiv (M_p)^j u_n \pmod{p},$$

for all $n \geq 0$. We also define $\Gamma_p := \Gamma_p(\mathcal{U}(a, b))$ to be the *cycle* of \mathcal{U} modulo p . The previously-discussed ideas can be extended easily to the sequence \mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} and we do so in the sequel. For brevity of notation, we occasionally write simply D, P, R, M, E and Γ for the previously defined quantities when the context is clear.

The following lemma gives some facts concerning the symmetry appearing in Γ . A proof can be found in [15].

Lemma 1. *Let p be an odd prime and let $j \geq 0$ be a fixed integer. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} u_{Rj-n} &\equiv (-1)^{n+1} M^j u_n b^{-n} \pmod{p} \quad \text{for } 0 \leq n \leq Rj \\ u_{Pj-n} &\equiv (-1)^{n+1} u_n b^{-n} \pmod{p} \quad \text{for } 0 \leq n \leq Pj \end{aligned}$$

For an odd prime p , we recall the *Legendre symbol*

$$\left(\frac{x}{p}\right) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \text{ is a quadratic residue modulo } p \\ -1 & \text{if } x \text{ is a quadratic nonresidue modulo } p \\ 0 & \text{if } x \equiv 0 \pmod{p}. \end{cases}$$

Lemma 2. *Let $\mathcal{U}(a, b)$ be a Lucas sequence as defined in (1), and let p be an odd prime. Then*

1. $R > 1$
2. $u_n \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ if and only if $n \equiv 0 \pmod{R}$
3. $p - \left(\frac{D}{p}\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{R}$
4. if $D \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, then $\frac{p - \left(\frac{D}{p}\right)}{2} \equiv 0 \pmod{R}$ if and only if $\left(\frac{-b}{p}\right) = 1$
5. if $\left(\frac{D}{p}\right) = 1$, then $p \equiv 1 \pmod{P}$.

Proof. Note that $R > 1$ since $u_1 = 1$. A proof of parts (2) and (4) can be found in [11], while a proof of parts (3) and (5) can be found in [3]. □

The following lemma follows from Lemma 3 in [6].

Lemma 3. *Let $b \neq 0$ be a fixed integer, and let $a > 0$ be an integer such that $D(a, b) > 0$. Then the sequence $\mathcal{U}(a, b)$ is nondecreasing for $n \geq 0$ and strictly increasing for $n \geq 2$.*

Lemma 4. *Let $b \neq 0$ be a fixed integer. Let $u_n(a, b)$ denote the n th term of $\mathcal{U}(a, b)$. Then*

$$u_n(-a, b) = (-1)^{n+1} u_n(a, b).$$

Proof. This follows from the Binet formulas for $\mathcal{U}(a, b)$ and $\mathcal{U}(-a, b)$. □

3. The Proof of Theorem 2

Proof of Theorem 2. Let b be a fixed odd integer. Let p be an odd prime such that $\left(\frac{-b}{p}\right) = 1$ and let $A_1 \in \mathbb{Z}$, with $1 \leq A_1 \leq p - 1$ be a solution to

$$x^2 \equiv -b \pmod{p}. \tag{4}$$

Note that $A_2 = p - A_1$ is also a solution to (4). Without loss of generality, assume that $A_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, so that $A_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Let

$$a_1 \equiv A_1 \pmod{2p} \quad \text{and} \quad a_2 \equiv A_2 \pmod{2p}$$

be positive integers with $(a_1, a_2) \neq (A_1, A_2)$, such that

$$D(a_1, b) > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad D(a_2, b) > 0. \tag{5}$$

Then $a_1 = A_1 + z_1p$ and $a_2 = A_2 + z_2p$, for some even integers $z_1, z_2 > 0$. Since

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}(a_1, b) &\equiv (0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, \dots) \pmod{2} \quad \text{and} \\ \mathcal{U}(a_2, b) &\equiv (0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 1, \dots) \pmod{2}, \end{aligned}$$

we see that

$$P_2(\mathcal{U}(a_1, b)) = 2 \quad \text{and} \quad P_2(\mathcal{U}(a_2, b)) = 3.$$

Thus,

$$P_2(W_{a_1, a_2}) = 6 \quad \text{and} \quad \Gamma_2(W_{a_1, a_2}) = [0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0]. \tag{6}$$

Since $a_1^2 + b \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ and $a_2 \equiv -a_1 \pmod{p}$, we have by Lemma 4 that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}(a_1, b) \pmod{p} = &(0, 1, a_1, 0, M, a_1M, 0, M^2, a_1M^2, 0, \\ &M^3, a_1M^3, 0, M^4, a_1M^4, 0, \dots) \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}(a_2, b) \pmod{p} = &(0, 1, -a_1, 0, -M, a_1M, 0, M^2, -a_1M^2, 0, \\ &-M^3, a_1M^3, 0, M^4, -a_1M^4, 0, \dots), \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where $M \equiv a_1b \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ is the multiplier of $\mathcal{U}(a_1, b)$ modulo p . Then both $\mathcal{U}(a_1, b)$ and $\mathcal{U}(a_2, b)$ have restricted period modulo p equal to 3. Let w_n be the n th term of \mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} . From (7) and (8), we see for $j \geq 0$ that

$$\begin{aligned} w_{6j} &\equiv w_{6j+2} \equiv w_{6j+3} \equiv w_{6j+4} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}, \\ w_{6j+1} &\equiv 2M^{2j} \pmod{p} \quad \text{and} \quad w_{6j+5} \equiv 2a_1M^{2j+1} \pmod{p}. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

It now follows from (6) and (9) that

$$w_n \equiv \begin{cases} 0 \pmod{2} & \text{when } n \equiv 0, 1, 5 \pmod{6} \\ 0 \pmod{p} & \text{when } n \equiv 0, 2, 3, 4 \pmod{6}. \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

For any

$$k \in \mathcal{A} = \left\{ 2pz \mid z \geq 1 \right\},$$

we conclude from (10) that each term of $\mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} + k$ is divisible by at least one prime in $\{2, p\}$. By (5) and Lemma 3, we deduce that \mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} is strictly increasing for $n \geq 0$. Thus, for any sufficiently large choice of $k \in \mathcal{A}$, it follows that $\mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} + k$ is primefree. Observe that the gap between consecutive terms of \mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} is increasing, while the gap between consecutive terms in the arithmetic progression \mathcal{A} is fixed. This phenomenon allows us to choose $k \in \mathcal{A}$ sufficiently large so that for some N , we have

$$w_N < k < w_{N+1}, \quad k - w_N > p \quad \text{and} \quad w_{N+1} - k > p.$$

Consequently, no term of either sequence $\mathcal{W}_{a_1, a_2} \pm k$ is zero or prime. □

We give an example to illustrate Theorem 2.

Example 1. Let $b = 3$ and $p = 13$. Note that $\left(\frac{-3}{13}\right) = 1$. Let $A_1 = 6$ and $A_2 = 7$. Then

$$A_1^2 \equiv A_2^2 \equiv -3 \pmod{13} \quad \text{and} \quad A_2 = 13 - A_1.$$

Let

$$a_1 = 32 \equiv A_1 \pmod{26} \quad \text{and} \quad a_2 = 33 \equiv A_2 \pmod{26}.$$

Observe that

$$(32, 33) \neq (6, 7), \quad D(32, 3) > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad D(33, 3) > 0.$$

Then, some simple calculations reveal:

$$\Gamma_2(W_{32,33}) = [0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0], \tag{11}$$

$$\mathcal{U}(32, 3) \pmod{13} = (0, 1, 6, 0, 5, 4, 0, 12, 7, 0, 8, 9, 0, 1, 6, 0, 5, \dots), \tag{12}$$

$$\mathcal{U}(33, 3) \pmod{13} = (0, 1, 7, 0, 8, 4, 0, 12, 6, 0, 5, 9, 0, 1, 7, 0, 8, \dots). \tag{13}$$

Adding (12) and (13) we see that

$$\Gamma_{13}(W_{32,33}) = [0, 2, 0, 0, 0, 8, 0, 11, 0, 0, 0, 5]. \tag{14}$$

Then, by layering two juxtaposed copies of (11) on top of one copy of (14), we have

n	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
$\Gamma_2(\mathcal{W}_{32,33})$	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0
$\Gamma_{13}(\mathcal{W}_{32,33})$	0	2	0	0	0	8	0	11	0	0	0	5

from which we can deduce (10). Finally, choosing

$$k \in \mathcal{A} = \left\{ 26z \mid z \geq 1 \right\},$$

with k sufficiently large, we see from (10) that each term of each sequence $|\mathcal{W}_{32,33} \pm k|$ is divisible by, but not equal to, at least one prime in $\{2, 13\}$.

4. The Proof of Theorem 3

The Proof of Theorem 3. Let $p \notin \{2, 17, 19\}$ be prime, let $b = 1$, and suppose that a is an integer such that $a \equiv m \pmod{646p}$, where $0 \leq m \leq 646p - 1$, and m satisfies one of the 16 systems of congruences in (2). Recall that

$$\mathcal{W}_{1,a} := \mathcal{U}(1, 1) + \mathcal{U}(a, 1),$$

where $\mathcal{U}(1, 1)$ is the Fibonacci sequence. Let $u_n(1)$ denote the n th term of $\mathcal{U}(1, 1)$, and let $u_n(a)$ denote the n th term of $\mathcal{U}(a, 1)$.

Since $a \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, it follows that $w_n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$ exactly when $n \equiv 0, 1, 5 \pmod{6}$. Since $a \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$, we have from Lemma 4 that $w_n \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ if $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. By inspection,

$$\left(\frac{D(a)}{17} \right) = -1 \iff a \equiv m \pmod{17}, \quad \text{where } m \in \{\pm 1, \pm 4, \pm 5, \pm 6\}.$$

Then, by Lemma 2, we have that $u_{9n}(a) \equiv 0 \pmod{17}$ for all $n \geq 0$, if $\left(\frac{D(a)}{17} \right) = -1$. Consequently,

$$w_{9n} \equiv 0 \pmod{17} \text{ for all } n \geq 0,$$

if $a \equiv m \pmod{17}$, where $m \in \{\pm 1, \pm 4, \pm 5, \pm 6\}$. Again by inspection, $u_3(1) = 2$, $u_3(\pm 4) = 17$ and

$$\left(\frac{D(1)}{19} \right) = \left(\frac{5}{19} \right) = 1 = \left(\frac{D(\pm 4)}{19} \right) = \left(\frac{1}{19} \right).$$

It now follows from Lemma 2 that if $a \equiv m \pmod{19}$, where $m \in \{1, \pm 4\}$, then

$$R_{19} \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, \quad 18 \equiv 0 \pmod{P_{19}} \quad \text{and} \quad M \equiv 1 \pmod{19}.$$

Thus, from Lemma 1, if $n \equiv m \pmod{18}$, where $m \in \{3, 15\}$, we see that

$$u_n(1) \equiv 2 \pmod{19} \quad \text{and} \quad u_n(\pm 4) \equiv 17 \pmod{19}.$$

Hence, $w_n \equiv 2 + 17 \equiv 0 \pmod{19}$. In summary, we have shown

$$w_n \equiv \begin{cases} 0 \pmod{2} & \text{when } n \equiv 0, 1, 5 \pmod{6} \\ 0 \pmod{p} & \text{when } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ 0 \pmod{17} & \text{when } n \equiv 0 \pmod{9} \\ 0 \pmod{19} & \text{when } n \equiv 3, 15 \pmod{18}, \end{cases} \tag{15}$$

which implies that w_n is divisible by at least one prime in the set $\{2, p, 17, 19\}$, for all $n \geq 0$. Then, using an argument similar to the one used in the proof of Theorem 2, it can be shown that for any sufficiently large value of z , no term of each of the sequences $|\mathcal{W}_{1,a} \pm k|$ is zero or prime, where

$$k = 2 \cdot p \cdot 17 \cdot 19 \cdot z = 646pz.$$

Consequently, each of the sequences $\mathcal{W}_{1,a} \pm k$ is primefree provided

$$a \equiv m \pmod{646p}, \quad \text{with } 0 \leq m \leq 646p - 1,$$

and m satisfies one of the 16 systems of congruences in (2). □

We give an example to illustrate Theorem 3.

Example 2. Let $p = 3$. Then by Theorem 3, there exist infinitely many positive integers $k = 1938z$ such that each of the sequences $\mathcal{W}_{1,a} \pm k$ is primefree for every $a \equiv m \pmod{1938}$, where

$$m \in \{80, 566, 650, 764, 794, 878, 992, 1106, 1220, 1364, 1478, 1592, 1706, 1790, 1820, 1934\}.$$

Remark 1. The smallest nonnegative value of m that satisfies all the congruences in a particular system in (2) for any prime $p \notin \{2, 17, 19\}$ is $m = 4$, when $p = 5$.

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